

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Chemical Modification of Salt Hydrates for Improved thermochemical Energy Storage
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	CMOSHIES
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Birmingham Centre for Energy Storage (BCES)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Thermochemical salt hydrate thermogravimetry cycle stability
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	April 8, 2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	May 4, 2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	April 8, 2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	May 3, 2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	0
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	
Number of days using the RI	26
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	"Using the RI" includes cycle stability experiments left to run during the weekends etc.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>Thermochemical energy storage (TCES) materials offer high energy storage densities, and systems based on the dehydration of common salt hydrates like $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been extensively investigated, though frequent problems such as agglomeration and unfavorable kinetics highlight the need for further material development. We consulted our VIENNA TCES-database and became aware of the Tutton salts, $\text{A}_2\text{M}(\text{XO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which have also been previously investigated as TCES materials, although their cycle stability had remained poorly characterized. We have already synthesized and partially characterized 41 mixed Tutton salts with the composition $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{M}_x(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Mg}, \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$); synthesis and phase- and elemental characterization of e.g. Fe(II)-containing salts is in progress.</p>	

These thermochemical energy storage materials are chemically tunable and thus, in contrast to simpler materials such as $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, can be tailored to dehydrate at different temperature levels, as confirmed by preliminary dehydration experiments using our Netzsch Jupiter STA. Particle size, thermal conductivity, heat capacity, and cycle stability are important properties to be measured at the host university. Expected outcomes of the research stay include the data necessary not only to elucidate the effect of different cations on the material's thermal behavior but also to carry out simulations for specific industrial use cases.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

User training was carried out on the devices listed below, and they were used on multiple different days.

1. Netzsch LFA 427 thermal diffusivity measurement (with Lloyd LS 100 plus press for sample preparation): the thermal diffusivity was measured of discs with a thickness of approx. 2 mm and a diameter of 12.7 mm, which were pressed and coated with graphite. Both strontium bromide (as benchmark) and 7 Tutton salts could be thus characterized, whereas calcium oxalate, as expected, failed to exhibit the required structural integrity after pressing.
2. Jeio Tech Temperature & Humidity Chamber: 100 cycles of dehydration at 135°C and rehydration at 40°C were conducted on 20 samples of 2 g each.
3. Mettler Toledo Thermal Analysis System DSC 3: specific heat capacity was determined for a wide range of Tutton salts, and dehydration enthalpy measurements were conducted before and after the cycle stability measurement.
4. Linseis simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) with water vapor inlet: key compounds were de- and rehydrated both before and after the cycle stability measurement.
5. Sympatec GmbH QICPIC particle sizer: the device was used for preliminary particle size measurement of strontium chloride samples.

Furthermore, training was conducted on the scanning electron microscope (SEM) TM3030 Hitachi as well as a Bruker D8 Advance powder diffractometer (XRPD). However, the high quality of the SEM and XRPD equipment at the sending institution (TU Wien) led to the prioritization of the use of other equipment at the hosting University of Birmingham.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

1. The thermal diffusivity measurements of the Tutton salts were highly reproducible and yielded values of ca. $0.4 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for $\text{SrBr}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ca. $0.25 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Cu}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Ni}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.
2. The cycle stability of the material library was analyzed both by STA for the most interesting samples and simple monitoring of the mass after a certain cycle count. Rehydration was complete or nearly complete after the 100th rehydration cycle based on mass change for the following samples: all measured Tutton salts $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Cu}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Co}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Ni}_{0.2}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Cu}_{0.5}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{K}_2\text{Zn}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, potassium oxalate, cobalt (II) sulfate, nickel (II) sulfate, and copper (II) sulfate. Substances displaying low

rehydration potential after 100 cycles under the measurement conditions include magnesium sulfate, iron (II) sulfate, zinc sulfate, calcium malonate, and calcium terephthalate.

3. The heat capacity measurements were conducted with a degree of reproducibility that allows for a rough estimate. After removal of outliers, the remaining Tutton salts had room temperature heat capacity values of 0.4 J/(mol•K) for $K_2Zn_{0.5}Cu_{0.5}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, 0.7 J/(mol•K) for $K_2Zn_{0.8}Ni_{0.2}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and 0.9 J/(mol•K) for $K_2Cu(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ at room temperature. Due to the large measurement error, however, it is plausible to postulate that no significant difference can be observed between the Tutton salts, especially since the heat capacity at higher temperatures appeared lowest for $K_2Cu(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, which actually had the highest value at room temperature.
4. Dehydration of samples on the Linseis STA occurred at a maximum temperature of 220°C, while rehydration was conducted at 40°C and 90% relative humidity. $K_2Zn_{0.5}Mg_{0.5}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $K_2Zn_{0.8}Cu_{0.2}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $K_2Zn_{0.8}Co_{0.2}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $K_2Zn_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $K_2Zn_{0.8}Ni_{0.2}(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $K_2Zn(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ displayed excellent rehydration capacity, whereas for $K_2Cu(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ the exact extent of the rehydration was not clear due to measurement artefacts, thus further measurements would be desirable.
5. The samples of pre-sieved $SrCl_2$ were successfully analyzed, and the particle sizes corresponded to reasonable expectations after the sieving process, thus paving the way for further measurements.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

1. The thermal diffusivity values obtained for the Tutton salts are close to that of a somewhat similar material, also a salt hydrate, $SrBr_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, rendering them plausible. Although the Tutton salts have a slightly lower thermal diffusivity, their much lower cost may render feasible the use of other materials in reactor design to improve overall thermal conductivity while keeping the overall price lower. It was to be expected that a change in the bivalent cation of an individual sample leads to a
2. The most obvious degradation occurred as expected with iron (II) sulphate, as iron (II) salts readily oxidize at elevated temperatures upon contact with air, and the successful positive control strengthens the reliability of the study. In preliminary studies using makeshift equipment at the TU Wien, high cycle stability of the Tutton salts for a few cycles had already been observed, so the findings at the University of Birmingham represent a thorough confirmation rather than a surprise. Magnesium sulfate is known to have sluggish rehydration kinetics, so this finding was also not surprising. Further studies will be necessary to determine under which conditions the calcium salts can exhibit cycle stability.
3. The heat capacity results obtained serve as a rough confirmation of the expected values and may serve as the basis for further simulation studies and planning.
4. Due to artefacts upon the sudden introduction of water vapor into the system, an exact comparison of rehydration kinetics appears difficult. However, first insights into the duration of the rehydration reaction can be gleaned, and in the attempt to enable exact rehydration kinetic measurements, future changes of the measurement profile may be undertaken.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

A variety of Tutton salts were characterized in terms of thermal diffusivity, heat capacity, and cycle stability upon de- and rehydration. Their cycle stability outperformed several other salts subjected to the same conditions, such as zinc sulphate.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

- One part of the press equipment necessary for thermal conductivity measurements was broken, but I was able to get it repaired quickly at the workshop (resulting in a delay of only ca. 2h).
- The Mettler Toledo Thermal Analysis System DSC 3 had not been recently calibrated.

Intended publications

The conducted experiments may be combined with XRPD and SEM analysis conducted at the TU Wien for a journal of relatively high impact factor, ideally e.g. The Journal of Energy Storage (Impact Factor 9.4). If this is not possible, a journal such as Crystals (Impact Factor 2.7) may be considered.

Data management

Project data will continue to be stored on the computers of the research group at the TU Wien and backed up in the TU Wien own cloud.

Conclusions / additional comments

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Substances used included cobalt (II) sulphate and nickel (II) sulphate. These are toxic to aquatic life and were thus handled carefully and disposed of in appropriate containers. The work bench was carefully cleaned before and after use.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Substances used included cobalt (II) sulphate and nickel (II) sulphate. These are carcinogenic and were thus handled carefully and disposed of in appropriate containers. The work bench was carefully cleaned before and after use.	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
Facilities skilled in the construction of phase diagrams e.g. for thermochemical energy storage materials would be of great benefit.											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
<p>1. It would be ideal if the research infrastructure list also included the details of how long it takes for the intrainstitutional bureaucratic processes to be completed (registration of all sorts at the host institution). This is also a helpful factor for applicants who are deciding where to conduct their research.</p> <p>2. It would also be ideal if the research infrastructure list were updated to state which devices are currently not available due to repairs, etc.</p>											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										

Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.